

How reliance on GenAI might limit human creativity and critical thinking in different fields - Categorisation of retrieved articles (Supplementary Material)

Abstract

Generative AI (GenAI) can greatly benefit Requirements Engineering activities by collaborating with humans and enhancing their creativity. On the other hand, GenAI tools are considered general-purpose AI models with systemic risk, partly because they can have a negative impact on human creativity and critical thinking.

Keywords

generative artificial intelligence, automation bias, mitigation strategies, trustworthy artificial intelligence

Using the search string “critical thinking” AND “creativity” AND (“generative artificial intelligence” OR “generative ai” OR “genAI” OR “gen AI” OR “large language model”), 398 accessible documents (either open-access or accessible through the authors’ institutions) in English were retrieved from Google Scholar, out of which only 389 were articles. Then, all titles and abstracts were used to filter out articles that do not mention AI and creativity or critical thinking in the title or abstract (either explicitly or implicitly). The papers were then classified into overlapping groups, based on their publication venue and the topics covered in each title and abstract, using deductive and inductive coding. During the deductive phase, the groups were combined based on set size and diversity on the discussed topics.

Ref.	Initial inductive notes	Deductive main categories (overlaps)
[1]	Business	AI-enhanced business
[2]	Business	AI-enhanced business
[3]	Skills	AI-enhanced business
[4]	Energy	AI-enhanced business
[5]	Industry 4.0	AI-enhanced business
[6]	Artificial Intelligence	AI-enhanced business; Arts and humanities
[7]	Artificial Intelligence	AI-enhanced business; Arts and humanities
[8]	Industry 4.0	AI-enhanced business; Arts and humanities
[9]	Education	AI-enhanced business; Education
[10]	Human-computer interaction	AI-enhanced business; Education
[11]	Management Education	AI-enhanced business; Education
[12]	Workplace AI Implementation	AI-enhanced business; Education
[13]	Academic Research Collaboration	Arts and humanities
[14]	Accounting and Finance	Arts and humanities
[15]	AI in Academic Writing and Research	Arts and humanities
[16]	AI Safety	Arts and humanities
[17]	Creativity	Arts and humanities
[18]	Artificial Intelligence	Arts and humanities
[19]	Artificial Intelligence	Arts and humanities
[20]	Artificial Intelligence	Arts and humanities
[21]	Artificial Intelligence	Arts and humanities
[22]	Artificial Intelligence	Arts and humanities
[23]	Artificial Intelligence	Arts and humanities
[24]	Artificial Intelligence	Arts and humanities
[25]	Artificial Intelligence	Arts and humanities
[26]	Human-Computer interaction	Arts and humanities

Ref.	Initial inductive notes	Deductive main categories (overlaps)
[27]	Artificial Intelligence	Arts and humanities
[28]	Social Media	Arts and humanities
[29]	Human-computer interaction	Arts and humanities
[30]	-	Arts and humanities
[31]	Art	Arts and humanities
[32]	Creativity	Arts and humanities
[33]	Data Analysis	Arts and humanities
[34]	Human-computer interaction	Arts and humanities
[35]	Design	Arts and humanities
[36]	Design and Art	Arts and humanities
[37]	-	Arts and humanities
[38]	Museums	Arts and humanities
[39]	Decision-making	Arts and humanities
[40]	Ethics in Artificial Intelligence	Arts and humanities
[41]	Ethics in Artificial Intelligence	Arts and humanities
[42]	Human-computer interaction	Arts and humanities
[43]	Games	Arts and humanities
[44]	-	Arts and humanities
[45]	Business	Arts and humanities
[46]	Business	Arts and humanities
[47]	-	Arts and humanities
[48]	Sociology	Arts and humanities
[49]	Music	Arts and humanities
[50]	Human-computer interaction	Arts and humanities
[51]	-	Arts and humanities
[52]	Public Administration	Arts and humanities
[53]	Smart cities	Arts and humanities
[54]	Smart cities	Arts and humanities
[55]	User Experience Design	Arts and humanities
[56]	-	Arts and humanities
[57]	Human-computer interaction	Arts and humanities; Education
[58]	Human-computer interaction	Arts and humanities; Education
[59]	-	Arts and humanities; Education
[60]	Art Education	Arts and humanities; Education
[61]	Art Education and Design	Arts and humanities; Education
[62]	Artificial Intelligence	Arts and humanities; Education
[63]	Arts Education	Arts and humanities; Education
[64]	-	Arts and humanities; Education
[65]	Digital Education	Arts and humanities; Education
[66]	e-Learning	Arts and humanities; Education
[67]	Education	Arts and humanities; Education
[68]	Education	Arts and humanities; Education
[69]	Education	Arts and humanities; Education
[70]	Education	Arts and humanities; Education
[71]	Education	Arts and humanities; Education
[72]	Education	Arts and humanities; Education
[73]	Education	Arts and humanities; Education
[74]	Education	Arts and humanities; Education
[75]	Education	Arts and humanities; Education
[76]	Education	Arts and humanities; Education
[77]	Education	Arts and humanities; Education
[78]	Education	Arts and humanities; Education
[79]	Education	Arts and humanities; Education
[80]	Education	Arts and humanities; Education
[81]	Education	Arts and humanities; Education

Ref.	Initial inductive notes	Deductive main categories (overlaps)
[82]	Education	Arts and humanities; Education
[83]	Education	Arts and humanities; Education
[84]	Education	Arts and humanities; Education
[85]	Education	Arts and humanities; Education
[86]	Education	Arts and humanities; Education
[87]	Education	Arts and humanities; Education
[88]	Education	Arts and humanities; Education
[89]	Education	Arts and humanities; Education
[90]	Education	Arts and humanities; Education
[91]	Education	Arts and humanities; Education
[92]	Education	Arts and humanities; Education
[93]	Education	Arts and humanities; Education
[94]	Education and Research	Arts and humanities; Education
[95]	Education Technology	Arts and humanities; Education
[96]	Education Technology	Arts and humanities; Education
[97]	Education Technology	Arts and humanities; Education
[98]	Education Technology	Arts and humanities; Education
[99]	Education Technology	Arts and humanities; Education
[100]	Education Technology	Arts and humanities; Education
[101]	Education Technology	Arts and humanities; Education
[102]	Education Technology	Arts and humanities; Education
[103]	Artificial Intelligence	Arts and humanities; Education
[104]	Artificial Intelligence	Arts and humanities; Education
[105]	Education	Arts and humanities; Education
[106]	Education	Arts and humanities; Education
[107]	-	Arts and humanities; Education
[108]	Educational Technology	Arts and humanities; Education
[109]	Educational Technology	Arts and humanities; Education
[110]	Educational Technology	Arts and humanities; Education
[111]	Foreign Language Education	Arts and humanities; Education
[112]	Higher and Adult Education	Arts and humanities; Education
[113]	Higher Education	Arts and humanities; Education
[114]	Higher Education	Arts and humanities; Education
[115]	Higher Education	Arts and humanities; Education
[116]	Higher Education	Arts and humanities; Education
[117]	Higher Education	Arts and humanities; Education
[118]	Higher Education	Arts and humanities; Education
[119]	higher education	Arts and humanities; Education
[120]	Language Education	Arts and humanities; Education
[121]	Language Learning	Arts and humanities; Education
[122]	Management Education	Arts and humanities; Education
[123]	Medical Education	Arts and humanities; Education
[124]	Human-computer interaction	Arts and humanities; Education
[125]	Human-computer interaction	Arts and humanities; Education
[126]	Social Media	Arts and humanities; Education
[127]	Tertiary Education	Arts and humanities; Education
[128]	AI System Design	Arts and humanities; Human-Computer Interaction
[129]	Human-Computer Interaction	Arts and humanities; Human-Computer Interaction
[130]	Human-Computer Interaction	Arts and humanities; Human-Computer Interaction
[131]	Human-Computer Interaction	Arts and humanities; Human-Computer Interaction

Ref.	Initial inductive notes	Deductive main categories (overlaps)
[132]	Artificial Intelligence	Arts and humanities; Human-Computer Interaction
[133]	Human-Robot Interaction	Arts and humanities; Human-Computer Interaction
[134]	Food	Arts and humanities; Human-Computer Interaction
[135]	Knowledge Management	Arts and humanities; Human-Computer Interaction
[136]	Cognitive Science	Arts and humanities; Psychology, neuroscience and healthcare
[137]	Healthcare	Arts and humanities; Psychology, neuroscience and healthcare
[138]	Healthcare	Arts and humanities; Psychology, neuroscience and healthcare
[139]	Healthcare	Arts and humanities; Psychology, neuroscience and healthcare
[140]	Neuroscience	Arts and humanities; Psychology, neuroscience and healthcare
[141]	Neuroscience	Arts and humanities; Psychology, neuroscience and healthcare
[142]	Neuroscience	Arts and humanities; Psychology, neuroscience and healthcare
[143]	Psychology	Arts and humanities; Psychology, neuroscience and healthcare
[144]	-	Arts and humanities; Psychology, neuroscience and healthcare
[145]	Psychology	Arts and humanities; Psychology, neuroscience and healthcare
[146]	Psychology	Arts and humanities; Psychology, neuroscience and healthcare
[147]	Artificial Intelligence	Arts and humanities; Psychology, neuroscience and healthcare
[148]	Chemical Engineering	Computer science and software engineering
[149]	Computer Science	Computer science and software engineering
[150]	Computer Science	Computer science and software engineering
[151]	Control Systems Engineering	Computer science and software engineering
[152]	End-user programming	Computer science and software engineering
[153]	Engineering Costing	Computer science and software engineering
[154]	Engineering Design	Computer science and software engineering
[155]	Engineering	Computer science and software engineering
[156]	-	Computer science and software engineering
[157]	Engineering	Computer science and software engineering
[158]	Software Engineering	Computer science and software engineering
[159]	Software Engineering	Computer science and software engineering
[160]	Software Engineering	Computer science and software engineering
[161]	General Intelligence	Computer science and software engineering; Arts and humanities
[162]	Artificial Intelligence	Computer science and software engineering; Arts and humanities
[163]	Cognitive Artificial Intelligence	Computer science and software engineering; Arts and humanities
[164]	Computational Humanities	Computer science and software engineering; Arts and humanities
[165]	Humanities	Computer science and software engineering; Arts and humanities

Ref.	Initial inductive notes	Deductive main categories (overlaps)
[166]	Machine Tool Industry	Computer science and software engineering; Arts and humanities
[167]	-	Computer science and software engineering; Arts and humanities
[168]	Education	Computer science and software engineering; Education
[169]	Computer Science Education	Computer science and software engineering; Education
[170]	Computer Science Education	Computer science and software engineering; Education
[171]	Computer Science Education	Computer science and software engineering; Education
[172]	Computer Science Education	Computer science and software engineering; Education
[173]	Computer Science Education	Computer science and software engineering; Education
[174]	Education	Computer science and software engineering; Education
[175]	Education	Computer science and software engineering; Education
[176]	-	Computer science and software engineering; Education
[177]	Education Technology	Computer science and software engineering; Education
[178]	Education Technology	Computer science and software engineering; Education
[179]	Education Technology	Computer science and software engineering; Education
[180]	Education Technology	Computer science and software engineering; Education
[181]	Education Technology	Computer science and software engineering; Education
[182]	-	Computer science and software engineering; Education
[183]	Educational Technology	Computer science and software engineering; Education
[184]	Engineering Design Education	Computer science and software engineering; Education
[185]	Engineering Education	Computer science and software engineering; Education
[186]	Higher Education Technology	Computer science and software engineering; Education
[187]	Information Technology Education	Computer science and software engineering; Education
[188]	-	Computer science and software engineering; Education
[189]	Programming Education	Computer science and software engineering; Education
[190]	Programming Education	Computer science and software engineering; Education
[191]	Software Engineering Education	Computer science and software engineering; Education
[192]	Human-Computer Interaction	Computer science and software engineering; Human-Computer Interaction
[193]	Neuroscience	Computer science and software engineering; Psychology, neuroscience and healthcare

Ref.	Initial inductive notes	Deductive main categories (overlaps)
[194]	AI education	Education
[195]	AI literacy	Education
[196]	-	Education
[197]	-	Education
[198]	Education	Education
[199]	Education	Education
[200]	Education	Education
[201]	Economics	Education
[202]	Education	Education
[203]	Education	Education
[204]	Education	Education
[205]	Education	Education
[206]	Education	Education
[207]	Education	Education
[208]	Education	Education
[209]	Education	Education
[210]	Education	Education
[211]	Education	Education
[212]	Education	Education
[213]	Education	Education
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[230]	Education	Education
[231]	Education	Education
[232]	Education	Education
[233]	Education	Education
[234]	Education	Education
[235]	Education	Education
[236]	Education and AI	Education
[237]	Education Technologies	Education
[238]	-	Education
[239]	Education Technology	Education
[240]	Education Technology	Education
[241]	Education Technology	Education
[242]	Education Technology	Education
[243]	Education Technology	Education
[244]	Education Technology	Education
[245]	Education Technology	Education
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[247]	Education Technology	Education
[248]	Education Technology	Education

Ref.	Initial inductive notes	Deductive main categories (overlaps)
[249]	Education Technology	Education
[250]	Education Technology	Education
[251]	Education Technology	Education
[252]	Education Technology	Education
[253]	Education Technology	Education
[254]	Education Technology	Education
[255]	Education	Education
[256]	-	Education
[257]	-	Education
[258]	Educational Technology	Education
[259]	Educational Technology	Education
[260]	Educational Technology	Education
[261]	Educational Technology	Education
[262]	-	Education
[263]	Education	Education
[264]	Higher Education	Education
[265]	Higher Education	Education
[266]	Higher Education	Education
[267]	Higher Education	Education
[268]	Higher Education	Education
[269]	Higher Education	Education
[270]	Language Education	Education
[271]	Language Education	Education
[272]	-	Education
[273]	-	Education
[274]	-	Education
[275]	-	Education
[276]	-	Education
[277]	Robotics	Education
[278]	Cultural Studies	Education
[279]	Teacher Education	Education
[280]	Education	Education
[281]	AI Ethics	Education; AI-enhanced business
[282]	Decision Making	Education; AI-enhanced business
[283]	Applied Linguistics	Education; AI-enhanced business
[284]	Biological Sciences and Medicine	Education; AI-enhanced business
[285]	Cognitive Science	Education; AI-enhanced business
[286]	Cognitive Science	Education; AI-enhanced business
[287]	Cognitive Science	Education; AI-enhanced business
[288]	Cognitive Science	Education; AI-enhanced business
[289]	Collaborative Work	Education; AI-enhanced business
[290]	Psychology	Education; AI-enhanced business
[291]	Business	Education; AI-enhanced business
[292]	-	Education; AI-enhanced business
[293]	-	Education; AI-enhanced business
[294]	Creativity	Education; AI-enhanced business
[295]	-	Education; AI-enhanced business
[296]	-	Education; AI-enhanced business
[297]	Design	Education; AI-enhanced business
[298]	-	Education; AI-enhanced business
[299]	Human-computer interaction	Education; AI-enhanced business
[300]	-	Education; AI-enhanced business
[301]	Human-Computer Interaction	Education; AI-enhanced business
[302]	Human-AI interaction	Education; AI-enhanced business
[303]	Information Systems	Education; AI-enhanced business

Ref.	Initial inductive notes	Deductive main categories (overlaps)
[304]	Machine Learning	Education; AI-enhanced business
[305]	Machine Learning	Education; AI-enhanced business
[306]	Management	Education; AI-enhanced business
[307]	-	Education; AI-enhanced business
[308]	Medical Writing	Education; AI-enhanced business
[309]	-	Education; AI-enhanced business
[310]	-	Education; AI-enhanced business
[311]	-	Education; AI-enhanced business
[312]	Natural Language Processing	Education; AI-enhanced business
[313]	Natural Language Processing	Education; AI-enhanced business
[314]	Human-computer interaction	Education; AI-enhanced business
[315]	Psychology	Education; AI-enhanced business
[316]	Human-computer interaction	Education; AI-enhanced business
[317]	Human-computer interaction	Education; AI-enhanced business
[318]	Psychology	Education; AI-enhanced business
[319]	Policy	Education; AI-enhanced business
[320]	-	Education; AI-enhanced business
[321]	-	Education; AI-enhanced business
[322]	Robotics	Education; AI-enhanced business
[323]	e-Commerce	Education; AI-enhanced business
[324]	User Experience Design	Education; AI-enhanced business
[325]	AI-human collaboration	Human-Computer Interaction
[326]	Human-Computer Interaction	Human-Computer Interaction
[327]	Human-computer interaction	Human-Computer Interaction
[328]	Creativity	Human-Computer Interaction
[329]	Human-Computer Interaction	Human-Computer Interaction
[330]	-	Human-Computer Interaction
[331]	Human-AI interaction	Human-Computer Interaction
[332]	Human-AI Interaction	Human-Computer Interaction
[333]	Human-Computer Interaction	Human-Computer Interaction
[334]	Human-Computer Interaction	Human-Computer Interaction
[335]	Human-Computer Interaction	Human-Computer Interaction
[336]	Human-Computer Interaction	Human-Computer Interaction
[337]	Human-Computer Interaction	Human-Computer Interaction
[338]	Human-Computer Interaction	Human-Computer Interaction
[339]	Human-Computer Interaction	Human-Computer Interaction
[340]	Human-Computer Interaction	Human-Computer Interaction
[341]	Human-computer interaction	Human-Computer Interaction
[342]	Human-computer interaction	Human-Computer Interaction
[343]	Human-Computer Interaction	Human-Computer Interaction
[344]	Human-Computer Interaction and Education	Human-Computer Interaction
[345]	Human-Computer Interaction Education	Human-Computer Interaction
[346]	Sociology	Human-Computer Interaction
[347]	Human-computer interaction	Human-Computer Interaction; Education
[348]	Education	Human-Computer Interaction; Education
[349]	Education	Human-Computer Interaction; Education
[350]	Education	Human-Computer Interaction; Education
[351]	Education Technology	Human-Computer Interaction; Education
[352]	Education Technology	Human-Computer Interaction; Education
[353]	Educational Technology	Human-Computer Interaction; Education
[354]	-	Psychology, neuroscience and healthcare
[355]	Neuroscience	Psychology, neuroscience and healthcare
[356]	Human-computer interaction	Psychology, neuroscience and healthcare

Ref.	Initial inductive notes	Deductive main categories (overlaps)
[357]	Human-computer interaction	Psychology, neuroscience and healthcare
[358]	Human-computer interaction	Psychology, neuroscience and healthcare
[359]	Healthcare	Psychology, neuroscience and healthcare
[360]	Healthcare	Psychology, neuroscience and healthcare
[361]	Human-Computer Interaction	Psychology, neuroscience and healthcare
[362]	Human-computer interaction	Psychology, neuroscience and healthcare
[363]	Neuroscience	Psychology, neuroscience and healthcare
[364]	Human-computer interaction	Psychology, neuroscience and healthcare
[365]	Psychology	Psychology, neuroscience and healthcare
[366]	Psychology	Psychology, neuroscience and healthcare
[367]	Psychology	Psychology, neuroscience and healthcare
[368]	-	Psychology, neuroscience and healthcare
[369]	Education	Psychology, neuroscience and healthcare; Education
[370]	Human-AI Interaction	Psychology, neuroscience and healthcare; Human-Computer Interaction
[371]	Agriculture	Sustainability
[372]	Artificial Intelligence	Sustainability
[373]	Career Development	Sustainability
[374]	-	Sustainability
[375]	Industry 4.0	Sustainability
[376]	Intelligent Systems	Sustainability
[377]	-	Sustainability
[378]	Sustainability	Sustainability
[379]	Psychology	Sustainability; Arts and humanities
[380]	Education	Sustainability; Education
[381]	Education	Sustainability; Education
[382]	Education	Sustainability; Education
[383]	Education	Sustainability; Education
[384]	Renewable Energies	Sustainability; Education
[385]	Education Technology	Sustainability; Education
[386]	Education Technology	Sustainability; Education
[387]	Education Technology	Sustainability; Education
[388]	Education	Sustainability; Education
[389]	Higher Education	Sustainability; Education

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